

Supplementary Material

Metformin prevents key mechanisms of obesity-related complications in visceral adipose tissue of obese pregnant mice

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Summary tables from proteomic screen of pgWAT at the middle of last trimester

Proteins named in the discussion are highlighted in each table.

Table 1: Significantly and relevantly upregulated proteins in pgWAT at G15.5 in HFD vs SD. 53 proteins are significantly (q-value < 0.05) and relevantly (fold change > 1.5) upregulated in obese (HFD) compared to lean dams (SD). Protein ID, protein name, gene, q-value (p-value corrected for multiple testing), fold change and valid values of both groups (= number of samples in which a protein was detected) are shown. The table is sorted according to fold change. 5 samples were analyzed per group.

Protein ID	Protein name	Gene	q-Value	Fold change	Valid values HFD	Valid values SD
P27601	Guanine nucleotide-binding protein subunit alpha-13	Gna13	< 0,01	6,92	5	0
Q6PGH2	Hematological and neurological expressed 1-like protein	Hn1l	< 0,05	5,72	5	0
Q0PD20	Ras-related protein Rab-34	Rab34	< 0,01	5,04	5	0
A0A0R4J0F6	Cyclin-G-associated kinase	Gak	< 0,0005	4,27	5	0
Q9WTQ5	A-kinase anchor protein 12	Akap12	< 0,01	4,23	5	5
Q9Z0F7	Gamma-synuclein	Sncg	< 0,05	4,03	5	5
P26645	Myristoylated alanine-rich C-kinase substrate	Marcks	< 0,05	4,03	5	5
Q3THG9	Alanyl-tRNA editing protein Aarsd1	Aarsd1	< 0,0005	3,88	5	0
Q8CG16	Complement C1r-A subcomponent	C1ra	< 0,05	3,83	5	0
Q6PE70	Integrin beta	Itgb5	< 0,001	3,35	5	0
Q8K0C9	GDP-mannose 4,6 dehydratase	Gmds	< 0,05	3,27	5	0
E9PUM4	Talin-2	Tln2	< 0,01	3,20	5	5
E9QA16	Caldesmon 1	Cald1	< 0,05	2,98	5	5
Q8BH58	TIP41-like protein	Tiprl	< 0,05	2,90	5	0
P06728	Apolipoprotein A-IV	Apoa4	< 0,0005	2,73	5	5
Q3UH59	Myosin-10	Myh10	< 0,05	2,69	5	5
O88492	Perilipin-4	Plin4	< 0,05	2,61	5	5
P17439	Glucosylceramidase	Gba	< 0,01	2,49	5	0
Q9DCC5	Chromobox protein homolog 3	Cbx3	< 0,05	2,32	5	5
Q63918	Serum deprivation-response protein	Sdpr	< 0,05	2,31	5	5
P10107	Annexin A1	Anxa1	< 0,001	2,16	5	5
P63024	Vesicle-associated membrane protein 3	Vamp3	< 0,05	2,15	5	5
B1AQF4	Dual specificity protein phosphatase 3	Dusp3	< 0,05	2,13	5	5
Q9Z0P4	Paralemmin-1	Palm	< 0,05	2,10	5	5
Q91VJ2	Protein kinase C delta-binding protein	Prkcdbp	< 0,05	2,09	5	5

Q9DBX6	Cytochrome P450 2S1	Cyp2s1	< 0,05	2,09	5	5
Q00898	Alpha-1-antitrypsin 1-5	Serpina1e	< 0,05	2,05	5	5
P07356	Annexin A2	Anxa2	< 0,01	2,04	5	5
Q61792	LIM and SH3 domain protein 1	Lasp1	< 0,05	2,04	5	5
Q8BGD9	Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 4B	Eif4b	< 0,05	2,01	5	5
Q8BJW6	Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 2A	Eif2a	< 0,05	1,98	5	5
P27546	Microtubule-associated protein 4	Map4	< 0,05	1,92	5	5
O54724	Polymerase I and transcript release factor	Ptrf	< 0,05	1,90	5	5
A0A0R4J034	Pyridoxal-dependent decarboxylase domain-containing protein 1	Pdxdc1	< 0,05	1,89	5	5
P31324	cAMP-dependent protein kinase type II-beta regulatory subunit	Prkar2b	< 0,05	1,83	5	5
Q61739	Integrin alpha-6	Itga6	< 0,05	1,81	5	5
P48036	Annexin A5	Anxa5	< 0,05	1,79	5	5
Q78IS1	Transmembrane emp24 domain-containing protein 3	Tmed3	< 0,05	1,75	5	5
E9Q8I9	Protein furry homolog	Fry	< 0,05	1,74	5	0
J3QNU6	Beta-arrestin-1	Arrb1	< 0,05	1,73	5	5
Q8R2Y2	Cell surface glycoprotein MUC18	Mcam	< 0,05	1,70	5	5
F8VQJ3	Laminin subunit gamma-1	Lamc1	< 0,05	1,70	5	5
Q6IRU2	Tropomyosin alpha-4 chain	Tpm4	< 0,05	1,66	5	5
Q9JIW9	Ras-related protein Ral-B	Ralb	< 0,05	1,64	5	5
A2AVJ7	Ribosome-binding protein 1	Rrbp1	< 0,05	1,63	5	5
P20152	Vimentin	Vim	< 0,05	1,60	5	5
F7AAP4	Calcium-transporting ATPase	Atp2b4	< 0,05	1,59	5	5
A3KGU7	Spectrin alpha chain, non-erythrocytic 1	Sptan1	< 0,05	1,58	5	5
E9Q616	AHNAK nucleoprotein (desmoyokin)	Ahnak	< 0,05	1,54	5	5
Q62261	Spectrin beta chain, non-erythrocytic 1	Sptbn1	< 0,05	1,54	5	5
P47955	60S acidic ribosomal protein P1	Rplp1	< 0,05	1,54	5	5
Q9CWF2	Tubulin beta-2B chain	Tubb2b	< 0,05	1,53	5	5
F8WIT2	Annexin	Anxa6	< 0,05	1,53	5	5

Table 2: Significantly and relevantly downregulated proteins in pgWAT at G15.5 in HFD vs SD. 143 proteins are significantly (q-value < 0.05) and relevantly (fold change > 1.5) downregulated in obese (HFD) compared to lean dams (SD). Protein ID, protein name, gene, q-value (p-value corrected for multiple testing), fold change and valid values of both groups (= number of samples in which a protein was detected) are shown. The table is sorted according to fold change. 5 samples were analyzed per group.

Protein ID	Protein name	Gene	q-Value	Fold change	Valid values HFD	Valid values SD
Q62264	Thyroid hormone-inducible hepatic protein	Thrsp	< 0,01	-12,47	5	5
Q9JK42	[Pyruvate dehydrogenase (acetyl-transferring)] kinase isozyme 2, mitochondrial	Pdk2	< 0,0005	-8,76	0	5
Q3V117	ATP-citrate synthase	Acly	< 0,0005	-8,52	5	5
F8VPN4	4-alpha-glucanotransferase	Agl	< 0,05	-8,32	5	5
Q5SWU9	Acetyl-CoA carboxylase 1	Acaca	< 0,001	-7,32	5	5
Q80Y98	Phospholipase DDHD2	Ddhd2	< 0,01	-6,98	5	5
Q99J39	Malonyl-CoA decarboxylase, mitochondrial	Mlycd	< 0,01	-6,34	0	5
Q8R2U6	Diphosphoinositol polyphosphate phosphohydrolase 2	Nudt4	< 0,05	-5,36	0	5
Q3TJZ6	Protein FAM98A	Fam98a	< 0,05	-5,17	0	5
A2AQN4	Acetyl-coenzyme A synthetase, cytoplasmic	Acss2	< 0,01	-5,15	5	5
A0A1B0GT63	Transmembrane protein 143	Tmem143	< 0,01	-5,09	0	5
Q9CQ20	Mid1-interacting protein 1	Mid1ip1	< 0,05	-4,85	0	5

Q8BGS7	Choline/ethanolaminephosphotransferase 1	Cept1	< 0,05	-4,81	0	5
P19096	Fatty acid synthase	Fasn	< 0,0005	-4,64	5	5
Q64521	Glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Gpd2	< 0,0005	-4,58	5	5
Q9CX10	2-methoxy-6-polyprenyl-1,4-benzoquinol methylase, mitochondrial	Coq5	< 0,05	-4,29	0	5
A2AQZ2	Phytanoyl-CoA dioxygenase domain-containing protein 1	Phyhd1	< 0,05	-4,15	0	5
Q9CR26	Vacuolar protein sorting-associated protein VTA1 homolog	Vta1	< 0,05	-4,05	0	5
B7ZMP1	Probable Xaa-Pro aminopeptidase 3	Xpnpep3	< 0,05	-3,93	0	5
G3UZY2	Thioredoxin, mitochondrial	Txn2	< 0,01	-3,88	0	5
Q8K0Z7	Translational activator of cytochrome c oxidase 1	Taco1	< 0,0005	-3,83	0	5
P06801	NADP-dependent malic enzyme	Me1	< 0,01	-3,78	5	5
D3Z4P2	VIP36-like protein	Lman2l	< 0,01	-3,47	0	5
Q8BHE8	Uncharacterized protein C2orf47 homolog, mitochondrial	Maip1	< 0,01	-3,41	0	5
P70444	BH3-interacting domain death agonist	Bid	< 0,01	-3,25	0	5
Q9D2R0	Acetoacetyl-CoA synthetase	Aacs	< 0,05	-3,17	5	5
Q99LB7	Sarcosine dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Sardh	< 0,05	-3,17	5	5
O08528	Hexokinase-2	Hk2	< 0,05	-3,07	5	5
P13516	Acyl-CoA desaturase 1	Scd1	< 0,01	-3,07	5	5
A2AKN9	Major urinary protein 6	Mup4	< 0,01	-3,04	5	5
P52196	Thiosulfate sulfurtransferase	Tst	< 0,0005	-2,99	5	5
Q9CZB0	Succinate dehydrogenase cytochrome b560 subunit, mitochondrial	Sdhc	< 0,05	-2,97	5	5
A0A1L1SRX2	AMP deaminase 3	Ampd3	< 0,05	-2,93	5	5
Q8JZU2	Tricarboxylate transport protein, mitochondrial	Slc25a1	< 0,01	-2,92	5	5
Q8VHY0	Chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4	Cspg4	< 0,05	-2,90	5	5
A0A0R4J0L6	28S ribosomal protein S35, mitochondrial	Mrps35	< 0,05	-2,88	0	5
A2A848	Peroxisomal acyl-coenzyme A oxidase 1	Acox1	< 0,05	-2,87	5	5
E9PXY1	Cullin-4B	Cul4b	< 0,05	-2,80	0	5
A0A140T8R8	DCN1-like protein	Dcun1d1	< 0,05	-2,76	0	5
Q8R086	Sulfite oxidase, mitochondrial	Suox	< 0,0005	-2,72	5	5
Q9D024	Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 47	Ccdc47	< 0,05	-2,71	5	5
Q9D6M3	Mitochondrial glutamate carrier 1	Slc25a22	< 0,001	-2,69	5	5
Q922B1	O-acetyl-ADP-ribose deacetylase MACROD1	MacroD1	< 0,05	-2,68	5	5
P30115	Glutathione S-transferase A3	Gsta3	< 0,05	-2,67	5	5
P40142	Transketolase	Tkt	< 0,05	-2,66	5	5
Q9DCW5	Cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6A, mitochondrial	Cox6a1	< 0,05	-2,65	5	5
S4R225	WD repeat-containing protein 13	Wdr13	< 0,05	-2,64	0	5
Q8K3J1	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 8, mitochondrial	Ndufs8	< 0,05	-2,64	5	5
Q8K411	Presequence protease, mitochondrial	Pitrm1	< 0,05	-2,63	5	5
Q9D6Y9	1,4-alpha-glucan-branching enzyme	Gbe1	< 0,0005	-2,60	5	5
Q9D023	Mitochondrial pyruvate carrier 2	Mpc2	< 0,05	-2,60	5	5
Q8CFR5	Dystrobrevin	Dtna	< 0,05	-2,59	0	5
Q99LY9	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 5	Ndufs5	< 0,05	-2,59	5	5
A0A0R3P9C8	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 9, mitochondrial	Ndufa9	< 0,05	-2,59	5	5
Q9CYV5	Transmembrane protein 135	Tmem135	< 0,01	-2,58	0	5
A0A0B4J1G1	Low affinity immunoglobulin gamma Fc region receptor II	Fcgr2b	< 0,05	-2,56	0	5

Q3URE1	Acyl-CoA synthetase family member 3, mitochondrial	Acsf3	< 0,05	-2,56	5	5
J3QMN4	Thioredoxin reductase 2, mitochondrial	Txnrd2	< 0,01	-2,55	5	5
A0A0R4J023	Methylglutaconyl-CoA hydratase, mitochondrial	Auh	< 0,05	-2,52	5	5
Q9QZA0	Carbonic anhydrase 5B, mitochondrial	Ca5b	< 0,01	-2,48	5	5
Q8CAY6	Acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase, cytosolic	Acat2	< 0,05	-2,47	5	5
Q8R164	Valacyclovir hydrolase	Bphl	< 0,05	-2,46	5	5
Q9D0I4	Syntaxin-17	Stx17	< 0,05	-2,44	0	5
O70589	Peripheral plasma membrane protein CASK	Cask	< 0,05	-2,43	0	5
Q9CPR5	39S ribosomal protein L15, mitochondrial	Mrpl15	< 0,05	-2,42	0	5
Q9CQZ5	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 6	Ndufa6	< 0,01	-2,39	5	5
E9QLB2	Lysophospholipase-like protein 1	Lyplal1	< 0,05	-2,34	5	5
Q9DBL1	Short/branched chain specific acyl-CoA dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Acadsb	< 0,01	-2,33	5	5
Q9CPQ1	Cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6C	Cox6c	< 0,05	-2,30	5	5
E9QNL5	Sulfotransferase	Sult1a1	< 0,05	-2,29	5	5
Q91VM9	Inorganic pyrophosphatase 2, mitochondrial	Ppa2	< 0,05	-2,28	5	5
Q9CR62	Mitochondrial 2-oxoglutarate/malate carrier protein	Slc25a11	< 0,0005	-2,27	5	5
Q8BWM0	Prostaglandin E synthase 2	Ptges2	< 0,01	-2,27	5	5
G5E8R3	Pyruvate carboxylase	Pcx	< 0,05	-2,25	5	5
F8WIU1	UPF0687 protein C20orf27 homolog	1700037 H04Rik	< 0,05	-2,25	5	5
Q9CQC7	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 beta subcomplex subunit 4	Ndufb4	< 0,01	-2,25	5	5
Q8K0C4	Lanosterol 14-alpha demethylase	Cyp51a1	< 0,05	-2,23	0	5
Q505D7	Optic atrophy 3 protein homolog	Opa3	< 0,05	-2,20	0	5
Q9ET01	Glycogen phosphorylase, liver form	Pygl	< 0,01	-2,17	5	5
A0A0R4J1R7	Pterin-4-alpha-carbinolamine dehydratase 2	Pcbd2	< 0,05	-2,17	5	5
P0DN34	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 beta subcomplex subunit 1	Ndufb1	< 0,01	-2,14	5	5
D3YUM1	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] flavoprotein 1, mitochondrial	Ndufv1	< 0,05	-2,10	5	5
O88696	ATP-dependent Clp protease proteolytic subunit, mitochondrial	Clpp	< 0,01	-2,10	5	5
Q9ERS2	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 13	Ndufa13	< 0,05	-2,10	5	5
Q99JR6	Nicotinamide/nicotinic acid mononucleotide adenylyltransferase 3	Nmnat3	< 0,05	-2,09	0	5
Q9D7J9	Enoyl-CoA hydratase domain-containing protein 3, mitochondrial	Echdc3	< 0,01	-2,08	5	5
Q99LS3	Phosphoserine phosphatase	Psph	< 0,05	-2,07	5	5
Q91WD5	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 2, mitochondrial	Ndufs2	< 0,05	-2,07	5	5
Q9CQQ7	ATP synthase F(0) complex subunit B1, mitochondrial	Atp5f1	< 0,01	-2,06	5	5
A0A1B0GT92	Glycogen [starch] synthase, muscle	Gys1	< 0,05	-2,03	5	5
Q99LC3	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 10, mitochondrial	Ndufa10	< 0,0005	-2,02	5	5
Q14DH7	Acyl-CoA synthetase short-chain family member 3, mitochondrial	Acss3	< 0,05	-2,01	5	5
P56135	ATP synthase subunit f, mitochondrial	Atp5j2	< 0,05	-2,00	5	5
Q9CQJ8	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 beta subcomplex subunit 9	Ndufb9	< 0,05	-2,00	5	5
Q7TMG8	Protein NipSnap homolog 2	Gbas	< 0,01	-1,99	5	5
P00405	Cytochrome c oxidase subunit 2	mt-Co2	< 0,05	-1,99	5	5

Q99P31	Hsp70-binding protein 1	Hspbp1	< 0,05	-1,93	0	5
Q91ZJ5	UTP--glucose-1-phosphate uridylyltransferase	Ugp2	< 0,05	-1,91	5	5
Q8CHT0	Delta-1-pyrroline-5-carboxylate dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Aldh4a1	< 0,05	-1,91	5	5
A0A0A0MQ68	Glutaryl-CoA dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Gcdh	< 0,05	-1,91	5	5
Q9DBL7	Bifunctional coenzyme A synthase	Coasy	< 0,05	-1,90	5	5
P35486	Pyruvate dehydrogenase E1 component subunit alpha, somatic form, mitochondrial	Pdha1	< 0,05	-1,88	5	5
Q9DCT2	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 3, mitochondrial	Ndufs3	< 0,05	-1,87	5	5
P03911	NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase chain 4	mt-Nd4	< 0,05	-1,87	5	5
P52480	Pyruvate kinase PKM	Pkm	< 0,05	-1,86	5	5
Q9QZD8	Mitochondrial dicarboxylate carrier	Slc25a10	< 0,05	-1,85	5	5
Q8BGC4	Zinc-binding alcohol dehydrogenase domain-containing protein 2	Zadh2	< 0,05	-1,82	5	5
Q91VT4	Carbonyl reductase family member 4	Cbr4	< 0,05	-1,82	5	5
Q8CG76	Aflatoxin B1 aldehyde reductase member 2	Akr7a2	< 0,05	-1,81	5	5
P97372	Proteasome activator complex subunit 2	Psme2	< 0,05	-1,80	5	5
P03888	NADH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase chain 1	mt-Nd1	< 0,05	-1,80	5	5
Q9QYR9	Acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 2, mitochondrial	Acot2	< 0,05	-1,80	5	5
Q9D0M3	Cytochrome c1, heme protein, mitochondrial	Cyc1	< 0,01	-1,79	5	5
Q9DC61	Mitochondrial-processing peptidase subunit alpha	Pmpca	< 0,05	-1,79	5	5
P14142	Solute carrier family 2, facilitated glucose transporter member 4	Slc2a4	< 0,05	-1,79	5	5
P05202	Aspartate aminotransferase, mitochondrial	Got2	< 0,05	-1,78	5	5
Q9DCJ5	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex subunit 8	Ndufa8	< 0,05	-1,77	5	5
Q9DB77	Cytochrome b-c1 complex subunit 2, mitochondrial	Uqcrc2	< 0,01	-1,77	5	5
Q92511	ATPase family AAA domain-containing protein 3	Atad3	< 0,05	-1,76	5	5
Q8CGK3	Lon protease homolog, mitochondrial	Lonp1	< 0,05	-1,74	5	5
Q8K2B3	Succinate dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] flavoprotein subunit, mitochondrial	Sdha	< 0,01	-1,72	5	5
P06745	Glucose-6-phosphate isomerase	Gpi	< 0,01	-1,72	5	5
Q3UW66	Sulfurtransferase	Mpst	< 0,05	-1,72	5	5
P55302	Alpha-2-macroglobulin receptor-associated protein	Lrpap1	< 0,05	-1,70	5	5
P12382	ATP-dependent 6-phosphofructokinase, liver type	Pfkl	< 0,01	-1,70	5	5
Q6PB66	Leucine-rich PPR motif-containing protein, mitochondrial	Lrpprc	< 0,05	-1,67	5	5
Q9R1J0	Sterol-4-alpha-carboxylate 3-dehydrogenase, decarboxylating	Nsdhl	< 0,05	-1,67	5	5
Q9D172	ES1 protein homolog, mitochondrial	D10Jhu81e	< 0,05	-1,64	5	5
Q9DAR7	m7GpppX diphosphatase	Dcps	< 0,01	-1,63	5	5
P47738	Aldehyde dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Aldh2	< 0,05	-1,62	5	5
Q8BQ47	Protein canopy homolog 4	Cnpy4	< 0,001	-1,62	5	5
Q9JMH6	Thioredoxin reductase 1, cytoplasmic	Txnrd1	< 0,01	-1,60	5	5
Q9D1D4	Transmembrane emp24 domain-containing protein 10	Tmed10	< 0,05	-1,60	5	5
Q9D6J6	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] flavoprotein 2, mitochondrial	Ndufv2	< 0,05	-1,60	5	5
O08749	Dihydrolipoyl dehydrogenase, mitochondrial	Dld	< 0,05	-1,59	5	5
P63325	40S ribosomal protein S10	Rps10	< 0,05	-1,58	5	5
Q8BGH2	Sorting and assembly machinery component 50 homolog	Samm50	< 0,05	-1,58	5	5
P15105	Glutamine synthetase	Glul	< 0,05	-1,58	5	5
Q03958	Prefoldin subunit 6	Pfdn6	< 0,05	-1,56	5	5

Q8R0Y6	Cytosolic 10-formyltetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase	Aldh111	< 0,05	-1,55	5	5
Q9CY27	Very-long-chain enoyl-CoA reductase	Tecr	< 0,05	-1,54	5	5
P28063	Proteasome subunit beta type-8	Psm8	< 0,05	-1,52	5	5
Q9R0X4	Acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 9, mitochondrial	Acot9	< 0,05	-1,52	5	5

Table 3: Significantly and relevantly upregulated proteins in pgWAT at G15.5 in HFD+MF vs HFD. 58 proteins are significantly (q-value < 0.05) and relevantly (fold change > 1.5) upregulated in obese dams treated with metformin during pregnancy (HFD+MF) compared to obese dams (HFD). Protein ID, protein name, gene, q-value (p-value corrected for multiple testing), fold change and valid values of both groups (= number of samples in which a protein was detected) are shown. The table is sorted according to fold change. 4 HFD+MF samples and 5 HFD samples were analyzed.

Protein ID	Protein name	Gene	q-Value	Fold change	Valid values HFD+MF	Valid values HFD
S4R211	Serine-rich coiled-coil domain-containing protein 2	Ccser2	< 0,05	13,01	4	0
Q9Z0Y1	Dynactin subunit 3	Dctn3	< 0,01	8,53	4	0
Q61555	Fibrillin-2	Fbn2	< 0,05	8,00	4	0
B1AZ15	Cordon-bleu protein-like 1	Cobll1	< 0,05	7,94	4	0
Q9CQR4	Acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 13	Acot13	< 0,05	7,46	4	0
Q99J39	Malonyl-CoA decarboxylase, mitochondrial	Mlycd	< 0,05	7,19	4	0
Q8K019	Bcl-2-associated transcription factor 1	Bclaf1	< 0,05	5,71	4	0
Q8K0D5	Elongation factor G, mitochondrial	Gfm1	< 0,05	4,87	4	0
D3YTQ3	Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein D-like	Hnrnpdl	< 0,05	4,80	4	0
Q99JC1	Ig lambda-2 chain C region	Iglc2	< 0,05	4,73	4	0
Q9QUT0	Ammonium transporter Rh type A	Rhag	< 0,05	4,69	4	0
Q59IW6	ABI gene family, member 3 (NESH)-binding protein	Abi3bp	< 0,05	4,44	4	0
Q9JK42	[Pyruvate dehydrogenase (acetyl-transferring)] kinase isozyme 2, mitochondrial	Pdk2	< 0,05	4,35	4	0
Q9D0R8	Protein LSM12 homolog	Lsm12	< 0,05	4,35	4	0
Q6GQT1	Alpha-2-macroglobulin-P	A2m	< 0,05	4,29	4	5
G3X9Q2	Guanine nucleotide-binding protein subunit gamma	Gng7	< 0,05	4,29	4	0
P52623	Uridine-cytidine kinase 1	Uck1	< 0,05	3,87	4	0
A0A0R4J1Z3	Transmembrane protein 33	Tmem33	< 0,05	3,86	4	0
Q9CPU2	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 beta subcomplex subunit 2, mitochondrial	Ndufb2	< 0,05	3,71	4	0
Q61584	Fragile X mental retardation syndrome-related protein 1	Fxr1	< 0,05	3,57	4	0
Q569Z5	Probable ATP-dependent RNA helicase DDX46	Ddx46	< 0,05	3,55	4	0
B1AUB9	Nuclear factor 1	Nfia	< 0,05	3,48	4	0
A0A0G2JER9	DnaJ homolog subfamily B member 6	Dnajb6	< 0,05	3,36	4	0
Q8CC86	Nicotinate phosphoribosyltransferase	Naprt	< 0,05	3,35	4	0
Q9D020	Cytosolic 5-nucleotidase 3A	Nt5c3a	< 0,05	3,34	4	0
F6RJ39	Apoptotic chromatin condensation inducer in the nucleus	Acin1	< 0,05	3,34	4	0
H3BL37	Treacle protein	Tcof1	< 0,05	3,30	4	0
Q3UE37	Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 Z	Ube2z	< 0,05	3,21	4	0
A0A0R4J1W7	Cell division cycle protein 23 homolog	Cdc23	< 0,05	3,08	4	0
Q9JI29	Phospholipid scramblase 3	Plscr3	< 0,05	3,08	4	0
Q3U422	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] flavoprotein 3, mitochondrial	Ndufv3	< 0,05	3,04	4	5
Q9D289	Trafficking protein particle complex subunit 6B	Trappc6b	< 0,05	2,88	4	5
D3Z2Z1	CAP-Gly domain-containing linker protein 1	Clip1	< 0,05	2,69	4	0
Q8VI75	Importin-4	Ipo4	< 0,05	2,69	4	5
Q9CPU4	Microsomal glutathione S-transferase 3	Mgst3	< 0,05	2,66	4	5
Q8C570	mRNA export factor	Rae1	< 0,05	2,40	4	0

Q3UID0	SWI/SNF complex subunit SMARCC2	Smarcc2	< 0,05	2,39	4	5
Q91V35	Receptor-type tyrosine-protein phosphatase	Ptpra	< 0,05	2,38	4	0
D3Z7P3	Glutaminase kidney isoform, mitochondrial	Gls	< 0,05	2,31	4	5
A0A0R4J0X5	Alpha-1-antitrypsin 1-3	Serpina1c	< 0,05	2,25	4	5
P30355	Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase-activating protein	Alox5ap	< 0,05	2,20	4	0
A2AEM2	Chloride channel CLIC-like protein 1	Clcc1	< 0,05	2,19	4	0
Q91VS7	Microsomal glutathione S-transferase 1	Mgst1	< 0,05	2,11	4	5
P22599	Alpha-1-antitrypsin 1-2	Serpina1b	< 0,05	2,05	4	5
P06728	Apolipoprotein A-IV	Apoa4	< 0,05	1,91	4	5
A0A0R4J170	Transcription activator BRG1	Smarca4	< 0,05	1,86	4	0
Q3UIA2	Rho GTPase-activating protein 17	Arhgap17	< 0,05	1,85	4	5
Q99LC5	Electron transfer flavoprotein subunit alpha, mitochondrial	Etfa	< 0,05	1,79	4	5
Q9Z0U1	Tight junction protein ZO-2	Tjp2	< 0,05	1,78	4	0
Q505D7	Optic atrophy 3 protein homolog	Opa3	< 0,05	1,71	4	0
Q9Z204	Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoproteins C1/C2	Hnrnpc	< 0,05	1,69	4	5
Q91XD7	Cysteine-rich with EGF-like domain protein 1	Creld1	< 0,05	1,64	4	5
Q9DB20	ATP synthase subunit O, mitochondrial	Atp5o	< 0,05	1,61	4	5
Q9QYJ0	DnaJ homolog subfamily A member 2	Dnaja2	< 0,05	1,61	4	5
P16858	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	Gapdh	< 0,05	1,58	4	5
P21619	Lamin-B2	Lmnb2	< 0,05	1,56	4	5
P54822	Adenylosuccinate lyase	Adsl	< 0,05	1,54	4	5
Q62465	Synaptic vesicle membrane protein VAT-1 homolog	Vat1	< 0,01	1,53	4	5

Table 4: Significantly and relevantly downregulated proteins in pgWAT at G15.5 in HFD+MF vs HFD. 45 proteins are significantly (q-value < 0.05) and relevantly (fold change > 1.5) downregulated in obese dams treated with metformin during pregnancy (HFD+MF) compared to obese dams (HFD). Protein ID, protein name, gene, q-value (p-value corrected for multiple testing), fold change and valid values of both groups (= number of samples in which a protein was detected) are shown. The table is sorted according to fold change. 4 HFD+MF samples and 5 HFD samples were analyzed.

Protein ID	Protein name	Gene	q-Value	Fold change	Valid values HFD+MF	Valid values HFD
P20065	Thymosin beta-4	Tmsb4x	< 0,05	-33,30	0	5
A0A0U1RNP7	Perilipin-1	Plin1	< 0,01	-15,75	0	5
Q9ERT9	Protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 1A	Ppp1r1a	< 0,05	-9,09	0	5
P58044	Isopentenyl-diphosphate Delta-isomerase 1	Idi1	< 0,05	-5,57	0	5
G5E870	E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase TRIP12	Trip12	< 0,05	-3,60	0	5
Q9Z0J0	Epididymal secretory protein E1	Npc2	< 0,05	-3,49	4	5
Q91XL1	Leucine-rich HEV glycoprotein	Lrg1	< 0,05	-3,40	4	5
Q62356	Follistatin-related protein 1	Fstl1	< 0,05	-3,16	4	5
Q9QXC1	Fetuin-B	Fetub	< 0,05	-2,60	4	5
Q8QZR5	Alanine aminotransferase 1	Gpt	< 0,05	-2,39	4	5
Q9DBX6	Cytochrome P450 2S1	Cyp2s1	< 0,05	-2,33	4	5
P51855	Glutathione synthetase	Gss	< 0,05	-2,28	4	5
P67984	60S ribosomal protein L22	Rpl22	< 0,05	-2,07	4	5
Q9D1X0	Nucleolar protein 3	Nol3	< 0,05	-2,05	4	5
Q9QZ06	Toll-interacting protein	Tollip	< 0,05	-2,03	4	5
Q9CXR1	Dehydrogenase/reductase SDR family member 7	Dhrs7	< 0,05	-1,97	4	5
P62897	Cytochrome c, somatic	Cycc	< 0,05	-1,96	4	5
Q9R099	Transducin beta-like protein 2	Tbl2	< 0,05	-1,93	4	5
Q9CQS8	Protein transport protein Sec61 subunit beta	Sec61b	< 0,05	-1,90	4	5
Q9ERE7	LDLR chaperone MESD	Mesdc2	< 0,05	-1,89	4	5

Q8R317	Ubiquilin-1	Ubqln1	< 0,05	-1,77	4	5
P63330	Serine/threonine-protein phosphatase 2A catalytic subunit alpha isoform	Ppp2ca	< 0,05	-1,74	4	5
Q9CQ65	S-methyl-5-thioadenosine phosphorylase	Mtap	< 0,05	-1,72	4	5
Q922Q8	Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 59	Lrrc59	< 0,05	-1,72	4	5
P17563	Selenium-binding protein 1	Selenbp1	< 0,05	-1,71	4	5
P70296	Phosphatidylethanolamine-binding protein 1	Pebp1	< 0,05	-1,71	4	5
A0A0B4J1E7	Importin subunit alpha-3	Kpna4	< 0,05	-1,70	4	5
Q9Z1Z2	Serine-threonine kinase receptor-associated protein	Strap	< 0,05	-1,69	4	5
Q61035	Histidine--tRNA ligase, cytoplasmic	Hars	< 0,05	-1,68	4	5
O08915	AH receptor-interacting protein	Aip	< 0,05	-1,67	4	5
Q3UGR5	Haloacid dehalogenase-like hydrolase domain-containing protein 2	Hdhd2	< 0,05	-1,67	4	5
P68037	Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 L3	Ube2l3	< 0,05	-1,66	4	5
Q91YJ2	Sorting nexin-4	Snx4	< 0,05	-1,64	4	5
O35945	Aldehyde dehydrogenase, cytosolic 1	Aldh1a7	< 0,05	-1,63	4	5
P57759	Endoplasmic reticulum resident protein 29	Erp29	< 0,05	-1,61	4	5
E9Q137	Testis-expressed gene 264	Tex264	< 0,05	-1,61	4	5
Q9QZ88	Vacuolar protein sorting-associated protein 29	Vps29	< 0,05	-1,58	4	5
O70274	Protein tyrosine phosphatase type IVA 2	Ptp4a2	< 0,05	-1,58	4	5
Q9DAK9	14 kDa phosphohistidine phosphatase	Phpt1	< 0,05	-1,57	4	5
Q91V41	Ras-related protein Rab-14	Rab14	< 0,05	-1,56	4	5
O35598	Disintegrin and metalloproteinase domain-containing protein 10	Adam10	< 0,05	-1,55	4	5
Q07797	Galectin-3-binding protein	Lgals3bp	< 0,05	-1,55	4	5
Q8BKE6	Cytochrome P450 20A1	Cyp20a1	< 0,05	-1,55	4	5
Q8JZN1	Macrophage galactose N-acetyl-galactosamine-specific lectin 2	Mgl2	< 0,05	-1,54	4	5
Q02819	Nucleobindin-1	Nucb1	< 0,05	-1,52	4	5